

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Project Acronym: **ERIGrid 2.0**

Project Number: **870620**

Technical Report Lab Access User Project

A Lightweight Private Blockchain-Based Secure Communication Framework For Events Monitoring and Control in the Smart Grid Ap- plications: BCF

Access Duration: 12/11/2023 to 09/12/2023

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced
Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

User Group Leader: Muhammad Faheem (University of Vaasa)

Report Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Access Project Number:	191
Access Project Acronym:	BCF
Access Project Name:	A Lightweight Private Blockchain-Based Secure Communication Framework For Events Monitoring and Control in the Smart Grid Applications
User Group Leader:	Muhammad Faheem (University of Vaasa)
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-Report-Lab-Access-User-Project-Access BCF-draft-vn.02
Report Version:	vn.n
Contractual Date:	13/11/2023
Report Submission Date:	09/12/2023
Lead Author(s):	Muhammad Faheem
Co-author(s):	-
Keywords:	Cybersecurity, Blockchain, Smart Grid, Internet of Things, Wireless Sensor Networks.
Status:	x draft, final

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
09/12/2023	v1.0	Muhammad Faheem (University of Vaasa)	First version for ICCS approval
15/01/2024	V1.1	Muhammad Faheem (University of Vaasa), Alkistis Kontou (ICCS)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1 Lab-Access User Project Information	8
1.1 Overview	8
1.2 Research Motivation, Objectives, and Scope	8
1.3 Structure of the Document	9
2 State-of-the-Art/State-of-Technology	10
3 Executed Tests and Experiments	12
3.1 Test Plan, Standards, Procedures, and Methodology	12
3.2 Test Set-up(s)	13
3.3 Data Management and Processing	14
4 Results and Conclusions	14
4.1 Discussion of Results	14
4.2 Conclusions	16
5 Open Issues and Suggestions for Improvements	16
References	17

List of Figures

Figure 1: Simulation design of the developed scheme	12
Figure 2. Number of nodes and the time spent on running create key, decryption, and signature operations in the wind turbines system	15
Figure 3. Number of nodes and the time spent on running updating smart contracts, signature verification, and encryption operations in the wind turbines system	15

List of Tables

Table 1. user project proposal	8
Table 2. preferred host laboratory/research infrastructure	8
Table 3. leader of the proposing user group	8
Table.4 Equipment and simulation parameters and their values	13
Table 5. wind turbine parameters	14
Table 6. Metrics used in the simulations.	14

List of Abbreviations

SG	Smart Grid
IoT	Internet of Things
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network
DER	Distributed Energy System

Executive Summary

The Smart Grid is expected to greatly enhance the efficiency and reliability of today's elderly electricity grid by employing advanced information and communication technologies. In smart grid, the IoT-enabled Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are considered as promising solutions due to their advantages, such as cable replacement, ease of deployment, flexibility, and cost reduction. IoWSNs can efficiently integrate, control, and monitor geographically DER in the smart grid. However, the inherent weakness of IoWSN has exposed critical power facilities to numerous security threats resulting in power grid operational failures and loss of synchronization. This operational failure may damage critical power system components which may interrupt the power supply and make the system unstable resulting high financial penalties. To address these issues, this research proposes a Lightweight Private Blockchain-based Secure Communication Framework (BCF) in IoWSNs for efficient and reliable data transmission in the DER applications. Theoretical analysis and extensive simulations using network simulation called RTDS will be carried out to verify the effectiveness of the proposed scheme for DERs in the SG.

1 Lab-Access User Project Information

1.1 Overview

Table 1. USER PROJECT PROPOSAL

User Project Acronym	BCF:
User Project Title	A Lightweight Private Blockchain-Based Secure Communication Framework For Events Monitoring and Control in the Smart Grid Applications
Main Scientific/Technical Field	Resilient and Secure Communications in Smart Grid Applications
Keywords (5 max., free text)	Cybersecurity, Blockchain, Smart Grid, Internet of Things, Wireless Sensor Networks.

Table 2. PREFERRED HOST LABORATORY/RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Laboratory Name	Electric Energy Systems Laboratory (ICCS-NTUA)
Proposed starting date of the access	13.11.23
Expected access duration (in weeks)	4 Weeks

Table 3. LEADER OF THE PROPOSING USER GROUP

Name	Muhammad Faheem
Nationality	Pakistan
Gender	Male
Age below 35-year-old (Y/N)?	N
Email address	muhammad.faheem@uwasa.fi
Organization name	University of Vaasa
Organization address	Wulffintie 32, 65101 Vaasa, Finland.
Organization website	www.uwasa.fi
Organization activity type	UNI - University and other higher education organizations

1.2 Research Motivation, Objectives, and Scope

The motivation behind this research stems from the imperative need for a secure and efficient communication framework within smart grid applications. Our primary objectives are to implement a lightweight private blockchain-based secure communication framework specifically tailored for events monitoring and control in the smart grid. The scope of this research encompasses the development, deployment, and evaluation of the proposed framework, with a focus on enhancing the security and reliability of communication processes in smart grid

applications. Particularly, this research implements a private blockchain architecture of Ethereum, including: (i) deploying decentralized smart contracts with specialized functions tailored for DER applications in the SG (ii) Implementing an advanced authentication and key agreement mechanism designed for users and DER systems within the SG, and (iii) conducting theoretical analysis and extensive simulations to validate the efficacy of the proposed scheme.

1.3 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 briefly outlines the state-of-the-art technology that provides the basis of the realised lab access. Section 3 briefly outlines the performed experiments whereas Section 4 summarises the results and conclusions. Finally, potential open issues and suggestions for improvements are discussed in Section 5.

2 State-of-the-Art/State-of-Technology

The rise of new digital technology known as Internet of Things, has lately gained a lot of interest from researchers and application developers [1,2]. Generally, IoT is incorporating two types of communication technologies (CTs), namely wired and wireless [3]. The key aim of both CTs at the communication layer is to provide highly stable networking for the automated exchange of information between different cyber-physical systems in the power grid [4-5]. Currently, most devices within the power grid are connected based on wired infrastructure working over industrial protocols to streamline management operations due to dynamic reconfigurable industry elements [6]. However, wireless solutions are increasingly playing a complementary role to wired solutions for strengthening the management and control capabilities of the power system elements. In this regard, IoWSNs are an invaluable technology for realizing the vision of SG, due to their low-cost identifying, sensing, networking, and processing capabilities [7]. In smart grid, the main attributes of IoWSNs are to enable smart integration, monitoring, and control of the distributed energy resources (i.e., Wind, Solar, Biomass, Geothermal, Hydroelectric, and Fuel/Gas) to increase economic benefits with the least breakdowns and maintenance costs in a bounded time interval [8-9]. With these objectives, IoWSNs have proved their importance in a wide range of smart grid applications as shown in Table 1 (Section 3) [1,10,11]. Importantly, all these applications would improve the day-to-day lives of ordinary citizens by ensuring the reliability of the electric power infrastructure with minimal human intervention [12].

Consequently, the smart grid integrates several thousand of power equipment to establish a dynamic and interactive infrastructure with new energy management capabilities to enhance the power quality and reduce electricity generation costs for end users [13]. However, such a heavy dependence on information networking inevitably surrenders the smart grid to potential vulnerabilities associated with communications and networking systems. Therefore, existing smart grid architectures are vulnerable to several kinds of cyber-attacks, such as Malware, Phishing, Sible, Denial-of-Service, Man-in-the-Middle, Insider Threats, and many others, meaning that hacking can lead to the whole network going down [14-16], resulting in a blackout and the destruction of infrastructures. Hence, smart grid security is crucial to maintain stable and reliable power system operation with less possibility of power grid collapse or equipment malfunction.

In the past, several researchers proposed conventional cybersecurity solutions to protect critical power system infrastructure from various types of cybersecurity attacks in the smart grid. For user privacy-preserving and data validity verification in smart grid, Li et al. [17] proposed a distributed in-network aggregation approach for smart grids to aggregate data along a spanning tree. Lu et al. [18] proposed EPPA to efficiently aggregate multidimensional data using a superincreasing sequence distributed by a trusted operation authority. PPMA proposed by Li et al. [19] further improves the EPPA to support multisubset data aggregation and security under malicious gateways. Xue et al. [20] also proposed an efficient and robust data aggregation scheme without a trusted authority for the smart grid, which not only ensures user's privacy and efficiency but also supports flexible dynamic user management with no need of involving a trusted authority. However, these existing works cannot provide a comprehensive solution to simultaneously implement user privacy protection, data integrity verification, public sharing, and permanent data storage, and most importantly, without trusted third parties. There are also some data aggregation schemes based on blockchain and homomorphic encryption. Ghadamyari and Samet [21] and Zheng et al. [22] combine blockchain and homomorphic encryption for data aggregation, though, their scenarios do not involve the issue of malicious aggregation gateways, which is a key issue in microgrid data

aggregation. For grid data dispatching, there are different optimization goals and algorithms. Most of the existing studies aim to propose better models and dispatching schemes. Bagherian and Tafreshi [23] utilized the PSO algorithm for microgrid power dispatching to maximize the profit of the management system. Kakigano et al. [24] combined fuzzy control with gain-scheduling techniques for voltage control. Khorsandi et al. [25] proposed a distributed control method employing the conventional droop control method, which enables accurate current sharing and desirable voltage regulation. Che et al. [26] proposed a three-level hierarchical coordinate strategy for power exchanges among neighboring microgrids. Although these works have conducted sufficient research on dispatching algorithms, how to securely implement these schemes in a distributed environment lacking trust is still an urgent issue to be solved.

In recent years, a novel idea of blockchain technology is proposed. Blockchain is a peer-to-peer (P2P) distributed ledger [27], which comes from the concept of the Bitcoin system. By design, the blockchain itself is resistant to tampering because the data in any given block cannot be retroactively changed without modifying all subsequent blocks [28]. In addition, the concept of the smart contract is rejuvenated with the aims to store information stored on a blockchain and execute automatically when prescribed terms and conditions are satisfied. Some studies introduce blockchain to solve the problem, e.g., [29-31]. However, most of these works aim at building a blockchain-based distributed energy trading platform, rather than providing a microgrid management system. Although [32] uses smart contracts for microgrid control, it does not implement the complex power dispatching process, but uses smart contracts to select a subset of power sources that participate in voltage regulation. In addition, existing consensus methods are used to get a collective agreement over a new transaction in a decentralized network. Consensus methods remove the need for trust and provide robustness such as the Proof of work (PoW) [33] is the first and well-known consensus method used by bitcoin cryptocurrency. Proof of capacity uses hard disk storage capacity [34] for mining instead of system's computing power as in PoW.

Proof of stake (PoS) [35] is similar to the PoW in which the miner node is generated by the monetary system to mine the new block. In Proof of Burn (PoB) [36], coins are burned and sent to some random address so that only those miners mine the block with the highest amount of burned coins. This consensus method is implemented only for cryptocurrency. Proof of Activity (PoA) [37] is a combination of PoW and PoS in which we solve the puzzle from the hash function and then validators sign on the block. In Proof of elapsed time (PoET) [38], every node in the network generates random time. Proof of X-repute [39] is a repute-based consensus method over IoT blockchain, which uses trust in a consensus protocol. Proof of block and trade (PoBT) [40] consensus algorithm and Credit-Based consensus mechanisms are used in a trust-based environment. Proof of Authority (PoAu) [41] is designed for cooperative blockchain in which the miner node has to reveal its identity to mine a block. The identity is used as a stake in PoAu. All aforementioned blockchain algorithms require high implementation complexity, computational power, and latency, and therefore cannot be implemented without modifications at the protocol stack level for smart grid applications.

3 Executed Tests and Experiments

3.1 Test Plan, Standards, Procedures, and Methodology

In the system that is being described, as seen in Figure 1, a network is made up of several sensor nodes that utilize blockchain technology. These sensor nodes are essential to the network's ability to collect data from many sources. After that, the collected data is sent to a centralized data storage server, creating an essential center for information administration and aggregation. A network architecture connects the sensor nodes to the data storage server, enabling a smooth data transfer from the sensing devices to the central repository. This architecture ensures the integrity and dependability of the data gathered by the sensor nodes by enabling effective and secure data handling. Moreover, the data storage server is closely connected to the Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS), a real-time simulator. The fact that this link is made via an internal network highlights how well the simulation tool and data storage infrastructure operate together. When modeling wind turbines and solar-powered energy systems, the RTDS is essential.

The ability to create dynamic and responsive models for renewable energy sources, such solar panels and wind turbines, is made possible by the real-time simulation tool. grasp these energy systems' behavior, performance, and possible problems requires a grasp of the modeling process. The real-world data gathered by the sensor nodes is accessed by the RTDS through interfaces with the data storage server, providing the simulation models with current and accurate data. To sum up, Figure 1's networked system illustrates the cooperation between sensor nodes running on blockchain, a centralized data storage server, and an RTDS (real-time simulation tool). In addition to providing safe and effective data processing, this integrated method offers sophisticated modeling capabilities for analyzing and optimizing the performance of solar- and wind-powered energy systems. Together, these components support the growth of a strong and adaptable network for sustainable energy management under various kind of cyberattacks.

Figure 1. Simulation design of the developed scheme.

The communication and security requirements for IEC 61850 and IEEE 802.11ac for wind-powered distributed energy resource applications are presented in Table 1.

3.2 Test Set-up(s)

In this study following simulation parameters have been used to perform simulations.

TABLE.4 EQUIPMENT AND SIMULATION PARAMETERS AND THEIR VALUES

Parameters	Value
Desktop Computer	OS(Linux/Window)
Simulation Tools	RTDS, RUST
Simulation environment	Python
Wind turbines	1, 3, 5
Nodes used in wind turbines	5
Router Switch	1 (24 ports)
Firewall	Checkpoint
Switches	Layer 1 and 2 (configurable)
IEEE or IEC Standard	802.11ab (Raspberry Pi 4), 61850 (Goose)
Transmission and control standards	IEC 60870-5-104, IEC 60870-5-101
Number of sinks	1
Transmission range of upper layer nodes	5 meters
Wireless communication, Ethernet	150Mbps
Transmitting rate of nodes	150kpbs
Packet size	1024 bytes
Number of channels	12
Data traffic load	Variable
Channel switching delay	30 μ s-50 μ s
Control packet size	40 bytes
Data aggregation power	0.55Watts(W)
Cost of a packet reception	0.95 W
Transmission energy of the nodes	88W
Memory size	32Mb
Network topology	Hybrid
Simulation time per epoch	60 seconds
Number of runs	10
Hurdle-1(irregular shape) height	5, 4.2, 3.7m
Hurdle-2(irregular shape) width	0.01-1m
Line of sight (LOS) and Non-line of sight (NLOS)	3.4, 2.6
Noise floor for both NLOS, LOS	-95, -91
Shadowing deviation	1.8

TABLE 5. WIND TURBINE (Vestas V82) PARAMETERS

Parameters	Values
Roto blade radius	41 m
hub height above ground	80 m
Wind Speed (cut-in / nominal / cut-out)	3.5 / 13 / 20 m/s
nominal turbine speed	14.4 rpm
Rated Power	1.65 MW
Rated MVA	1.808 MVA
Reactive power consumption (@rated power)	0.740 MVar
Reactive power consumption (@ no load)	0.447 MVar
induction machine	6 pole, 1200 rpm
stator voltage (60 Hz. Operation)	600 Volts I-I rms (Y-gnd)
Power Factor Correction Capacitors (standard)	499.4 kVAr (22.7 kVAr steps)

TABLE 6. METRICS USED IN THE SIMULATIONS.

Metrics	Definition
Latency	It is 'how much time a data packet takes to travel from one designated nodeA to another nodeB in the network'.
Distributed Denial of Service Attacks (DDoS)	It is ' a perpetrator seeks to make nodesA resources unavailable to its intended NodeB or user by temporarily or indefinitely disrupting services in a connected network'.

3.3 Data Management and Processing

The central server, which is a crucial element that directly communicates with the simulation models created in the Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS), is the focal point of the system's data collecting procedure, as was mentioned in Section 3.1. Most importantly, the RTDS, an advanced real-time simulation tool, is seamlessly connected to the central server. This direct interface shows that the simulation models and the data collection infrastructure which is based on sensor nodes are tightly integrated. The central server provides a dynamic and responsive sensor modeling environment which interacts with the wind and solar powered simulation models operating on RTDS in real-time.

4 Results and Conclusions

4.1 Discussion of Results

The procedures of key creation, decryption, and signature in the BCWSNs are depicted in Figure 2. For the randomly chosen nodes in the wind turbines control and monitoring system, it is evident that the maximum and minimum latency values of the creation key fluctuate between 3.80 and 0.03. For the randomly chosen nodes in the wind turbines system, the high and low decryption latency values are found to be between 1.74 and 0.0013. Furthermore, the wind turbines system's maximum and minimum latency values for signature operations

for the randomly chosen nodes are noted to range from 1.44 to 0.01. Figure 2 shows that in the wind turbines system, the creation key delay value is higher than the decryption and signing processes combined. However, the decryption latency number is marginally higher than the signature operations, and both delay values typically overlap.

Figure 3 shows the BCWSN's encryption, signature verification, and smart contract update processes. It is noted that for the randomly chosen nodes in the wind turbines system, the high and low latency values of updating smart contracts vary between 0.44 and 0.14. Conversely, the encryption and signature verification maximum and minimum latency values are fluctuating between 0.2053 and 0.286 and 0.34 and 0.493, respectively. Figure 3 data unambiguously demonstrates that the encryption delay value is minimal when compared to the wind turbines system's signature verification and smart contracts. In a wind turbines system, the delay values for signature verification and encryption coincide most of the time. As seen in Figure 3, the delay value of smart contracts is high when compared to encryption and signature verification.

Figure 2. Number of nodes and the time spent on running create key, decryption, and signature operations in the wind turbines system.

Figure 3. Number of nodes and the time spent on running updating smart contracts, signature verification, and encryption operations in the wind turbines system.

4.2 Conclusions

In this study, a secure communication framework (BCF) that is built on a Lightweight Private Blockchain is implemented to address these security issues during data transmission for DER applications in the smart grid is the goal. In order to assess how well the suggested BCF addresses security flaws and improves the overall resilience of the smart grid, a thorough theoretical analysis and extensive simulations utilizing the Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) was implemented. The simulation data and results showed that the proposed scheme significantly improve the data reliability, resilience, and security of the DERs in the smart grid.

5 Open Issues and Suggestions for Improvements

In the future, the research will examine the proposed scheme under diverse cyberattack scenarios that were not addressed in this study. Furthermore, integrating modern technologies with the Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) will necessitate a comprehensive reconfiguration of the protocol stack at the Goose protocol level, operating in accordance with the IEC 61850 standard.

References

- [1] Faheem, Muhammad, et al. *Smart grid communication and information technologies in the perspective of Industry 4.0: Opportunities and challenges*. *Computer Science Review*, 2018, 30: 1-30.
- [2] Faheem, M., & Gungor, V. C. (2018). *Energy efficient and QoS-aware routing protocol for wireless sensor network-based smart grid applications in the context of industry 4.0*. *Applied Soft Computing*, 68, 910-922.
- [3] Zhao, X., Askari, H., Chen, J. (2021). *Nanogenerators for smart cities in the era of 5G and Internet of Things*. *Joule*, 5(6), 1391-1431.
- [4] Fadel, E., Faheem, M., Gungor, V. C., ... & Akyildiz, I. F. (2017). *Spectrum-aware bio-inspired routing in cognitive radio sensor networks for smart grid applications*. *Computer Communications*, 101, 106-120.
- [5] Neffati, O. S., Sengan, S., Thangavelu, K. D., Kumar, S. D., Setiawan, R., Elangovan, M., ... Ve- layutham, P. (2021). *Migrating from traditional grid to smart grid in smart cities promoted in developing country*. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 45, 101125.
- [6] Maddikunta, P. K. R., Pham, Q. V., Prabadevi, B., Deepa, N., Dev, K., Gadekallu, T. R., ... Liyanage, M. (2022). *Industry 5.0: A survey on enabling technologies and potential applications*. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 26, 100257.
- [7] Faheem, M., & Gungor, V. C. (2018). *MQRP: Mobile sinks-based QoS-aware data gathering protocol for wireless sensor networks-based smart grid applications in the context of industry 4.0-based on internet of things*. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 82, 358-374.
- [8] Li, M., Hamawandy, N. M., Wahid, F., Rjoub, H., Bao, Z. (2021). *Renewable energy resources investment and green finance: Evidence from China*. *Resources Policy*, 74, 102402.
- [9] Ecer, F., Pamucar, D., Mardani, A., Alrasheedi, M. (2021). *Assessment of renewable energy re- sources using new interval rough number extension of the level based weight assessment and combinative distance-based assessment*. *Renewable Energy*, 170, 1156-1177.
- [10] Faheem, M., & Gungor, V. C. (2017). *Capacity and spectrum-aware communication framework for wireless sensor network-based smart grid applications*. *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, 53, 48-58.
- [11] Abrahamsen, F. E., Ai, Y., Cheffena, M. (2021). *Communication technologies for smart grid: A comprehensive survey*. *Sensors*, 21(23), 8087.
- [12] Faheem, Muhammad, et al. *Bio-inspired routing protocol for WSN-based smart grid applications in the context of Industry 4.0*. *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, 2019, 30.8: e3503.
- [13] Gungor, V. C., & Hancke, G. P. (2009). *Industrial wireless sensor networks: Challenges, design principles, and technical approaches*. *IEEE Transactions on industrial electronics*, 56(10), 4258-4265.
- [14] Almasarani, A., Majid, M. A. (2021). *5G-Wireless sensor networks for smart grid-*

- accelerating technology's progress and innovation in the kingdom of Saudi arabia. Procedia Computer Science, 182, 46-55.*
- [15] Tufail, S., Parvez, I., Batool, S., Sarwat, A. (2021). A survey on cybersecurity challenges, detection, and mitigation techniques for the smart grid. *Energies, 14(18), 5894.*
- [16] Mohammadi, F. (2021). Emerging challenges in smart grid cybersecurity enhancement: A review. *Energies, 14(5), 1380.*
- [17] F. Li, B. Luo, and P. Liu, "Secure information aggregation for smart grids using homomorphic encryption," in *Proc. 1st IEEE Int. Conf. Smart Grid Commun. (SmartGridComm)*, Gaithersburg, MD, USA, 2010, pp. 327–332.
- [18] R. Lu, X. Liang, X. Li, X. Lin, and X. Shen, "EPPA: An efficient and privacy-preserving aggregation scheme for secure smart grid communications," *IEEE Trans. Parallel Distrib. Syst., vol. 23, no. 9, pp. 1621–1631, Sep. 2012.*
- [19] S. Li, K. Xue, Q. Yang, and P. Hong, "PPMA: Privacy-preserving multisubset data aggregation in smart grid," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informat., vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 462–471, Feb. 2018.*
- [20] K. Xue, B. Zhu, Q. Yang, D. S. L. Wei, and M. Guizani, "An efficient and robust data aggregation scheme without a trusted authority for smart grid," *IEEE Internet Things J., vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1949–1959, Mar. 2020.*
- [21] M. Ghadamyari and S. Samet, "Privacy-preserving statistical analysis of health data using paillier homomorphic encryption and permissioned blockchain," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Big Data (BigData)*, Los Angeles, CA, USA, 2019, pp. 5474–5479. [22] B.-K. Zheng et al., "Scalable and privacy preserving data sharing based on blockchain," *J. Comput. Sci. Technol., vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 557–567, 2018.*
- [23] A. Bagherian and S. M. M. Tafreshi, "A developed energy management system for a microgrid in the competitive electricity market," in *Proc. IEEE Bucharest PowerTech, Bucharest, Romania, 2009, pp. 1–6.*
- [24] H. Kakigano, Y. Miura, and T. Ise, "Distribution voltage control for DC microgrids using fuzzy control and gain-scheduling technique," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron., vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 2246–2258, May 2013.*
- [25] A. Khorsandi, M. Ashourloo, and H. Mokhtari, "A decentralized control method for a low-voltage DC microgrid," *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers., vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 793–801, Dec. 2014.*
- [26] L. Che, M. Shahidehpour, and A. S. Alabdulwahab and Y. Al-Turki, "Hierarchical coordination of a community microgrid with AC and DC microgrids," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 3042–3051, Nov. 2015.*
- [27] Esmailian, B., Sarkis, J., Lewis, K., Behdad, S. (2020). Blockchain for the future of sustainable supply chain management in Industry 4.0. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 163, 105064.*
- [28] Cole, R., Stevenson, M., Aitken, J. (2019). Blockchain technology: implications for operations and supply chain management. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal.*
- [29] L. Xue, Y. Teng, Z. Zhang, J. Li, K. Wang, and Q. Huang, "Blockchain technology for electricity market in microgrid," in *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Power Renew. Energy (ICPRE)*, Chengdu, China, 2017, pp. 704–708.

- [30] E. Mengelkamp, B. Notheisen, C. Beer, D. Dauer, and C. Weinhardt, "A blockchain-based smart grid: Towards sustainable local energy markets," *Comput. Sci. Res. Develop.*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 207–214, 2018.
- [31] Z. Li, J. Kang, R. Yu, D. Ye, Q. Deng, and Y. Zhang, "Consortium blockchain for secure energy trading in industrial Internet of Things," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informat.*, vol. 14, no. 8, pp. 3690–3700, Aug. 2018.
- [32] P. Danzi, M. Angjelichinoski, C. Stefanovic, and P. Popovski, "Distributed proportional-fairness control in microgrids via blockchain smart contracts," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Smart Grid Commun. (Smart-GridComm)*, Dresden, Germany, 2017, pp. 45–51.
- [33] Qu, Q., Xu, R., Chen, Y., Blasch, E., Aved, A. (2021). Enable Fair Proof-of-Work (PoW) Consensus for Blockchains in IoT by Miner Twins (MinT). *Future Internet*, 13(11), 291.
- [34] Ezzine, R., Wiese, M., Deppe, C., Boche, H. (2022, June). A Rigorous Proof of the Capacity of MIMO Gauss-Markov Rayleigh Fading Channels. In *2022 IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory (ISIT)* (pp. 2732-2737). IEEE.
- [35] Saad, M., Qin, Z., Ren, K., Nyang, D., Mohaisen, D. (2021). e-pos: Making proof-of-stake decentralized and fair. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, 32(8), 1961-1973.
- [36] Karantias, K., Kiayias, A., Zindros, D. (2020, February). Proof-of-burn. In *International conference on financial cryptography and data security* (pp. 523-540). Springer, Cham.
- [37] Wang, D., Jin, C., Li, H., Perkowski, M. (2020, September). Proof of activity consensus algorithm based on credit reward mechanism. In *International Conference on Web Information Systems and Applications* (pp. 618-628). Springer.
- [38] Bowman, M., Das, D., Mandal, A., Montgomery, H. (2021, December). On elapsed time consensus protocols. In *International Conference on Cryptology in India* (pp. 559-583). Springer, Cham.
- [39] Tang, X., Hu, G., Yuan, Y., Li, H., Zhang, Y., Li, Y., ... Cheng, J. (2021, July). Survey: Research on Blockchain Consensus Mechanism in IoT Security. In *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Security* (pp. 573-584). Springer.
- [40] Nam Nguyen, H., Anh Tran, H., Fowler, S., Souihi, S. (2021). A survey of Blockchain technologies applied to software-defined networking: Research challenges and solutions. *IET Wireless Sensor Systems*, 11(6), 233-247.
- [41] Yang, J., Dai, J., Gooi, H. B., Nguyen, H., Paudel, A. (2022). A Proof-of-Authority Blockchain Based Distributed Control System for Islanded Microgrids. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

